

LEVEL OPERATORS ON INTUITIONISTIC L-FUZZY SETS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we propose the Level Operators on Intuitionistic L-Fuzzy Sets and establish some of their properties.

Key Words: Fuzzy Set, Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set, Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets Of Second Type & Intuitionistic L-Fuzzy Set

1. Introduction:

Fuzzy sets were introduced by Lotfi. A. Zadeh in 1965 as a generalisation of classical (crisp) sets. Further the fuzzy sets are generalised by Krassimir.T. Atanassov in which he has taken non-membership values also into consideration and introduced Intuitionistic Fuzzy sets [IFS] and their extensions like Intuitionistic Fuzzy sets of second type [IFSST], Intuitionistic L-Fuzzy sets [ILFS] and Temporal Intuitionistic Fuzzy sets [TIFS]. In section 2, we give some basic definitions and in section 3, we introduce the Level operators on ILFS in the universal set E and establish some of their properties. The paper is concluded in section 4.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section, we give some basic definitions.

Definition 2.1: A Fuzzy set [FS]A in a universal set E is defined by

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \rangle / x \in E \},$$

Where $\mu_A: E \rightarrow [0,1]$ is the membership function representing the membership degree of element x in the FS A such that $0 \leq \mu_A(x) \leq 1$.

Definition 2.2: An Intuitionistic Fuzzy set [IFS]A in a universal set E is defined as an object of the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle / x \in E \},$$

Where $\mu_A: E \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\nu_A: E \rightarrow [0,1]$ denote the degree of membership and the degree of non-membership of the element x in E respectively, satisfying $0 \leq \mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1$.

The value $\pi_A(x) = 1 - \mu_A(x) - \nu_A(x)$ is the degree of uncertainty of the element $x \in E$ to the IFS A.

Definition 2.3: An Intuitionistic Fuzzy sets of second type [IFSST]A in a universal set E is defined as an object of the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle / x \in E \},$$

Where $\mu_A: E \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\nu_A: E \rightarrow [0,1]$ denote the degree of membership and the degree of non-membership of the element $x \in E$ respectively, satisfying $0 \leq \mu_A(x)^2 + \nu_A(x)^2 \leq 1$.

The value $\pi_A(x) = \sqrt{1 - \mu_A(x)^2 + \nu_A(x)^2}$ is the degree of uncertainty of the element $x \in E$ to the IFSST A.

Definition 2.4: An Intuitionistic L-Fuzzy set [ILFS] A in a universal set E is defined as an object of the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle / x \in E \},$$

where $\mu_A: E \rightarrow L$ and $\nu_A: E \rightarrow L$ denote the degree of membership and the degree of non-membership of the element $x \in E$ respectively, satisfying $\mu_A(x) \leq N(\nu_A(x))$, $N: L \rightarrow L$ is a unary involute order reversing operation and E be fixed.

The value $\pi_A(x) = N(\sup((\mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)))$ is the degree of uncertainty of the element $x \in E$ to the *ILFS* A .

3. Level Operators on Intuitionistic L-Fuzzy Sets:

In this section, we define the Level operators on *ILFS* in the universal set E and establish some of their properties.

The following two operators $!(A)$ and $?(A)$

$$!(A) = \{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \},$$

$$?(A) = \{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \},$$

are called the Level Operators on the *ILFS* A .

Example 3.1:

Let $E = \{a, b, c\}$ and Let the *ILFS* A is,

$$A = \{ \langle a, 0.4, 0.3 \rangle, \langle b, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle, \langle c, 0.2, 0.6 \rangle \}$$

$$\text{then } !A = \{ \langle a, 0.5, 0.3 \rangle, \langle b, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle, \langle c, 0.5, 0.5 \rangle \}$$

$$\text{and } ?A = \{ \langle a, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, \langle b, 0.5, 0.5 \rangle, \langle c, 0.2, 0.6 \rangle \}$$

are the Level Operators on A .

Theorem 3.1: For any *ILFS* A , we have

(a) $!(A) = \overline{?(A)}$,

(b) $!(A) = A \cup \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \}$,

(c) $?(A) = A \cap \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \}$,

(d) $!(?(A)) = ?(!(A)) = \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \}$.

Proof:

(a) $?(A) = \overline{?(\overline{A})}$

$$\overline{?(A)} = \overline{\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \}}$$

$$\overline{?(A)} = \{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \}$$

$$\overline{?(A)} = !(A).$$

(b) $A \cup \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \} = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle / x \in E \} \cup \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \}$

$$A \cup \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \} = \{ \langle x, \sup\left(\mu_A(x), \frac{1}{2}\right), \inf\left(\nu_A(x), \frac{1}{2}\right) \rangle / x \in E \}$$

$$A \cup \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \} = \{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \}$$

$$A \cup \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \} = !(A).$$

(c) $A \cap \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \} = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle / x \in E \} \cap \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \}$

$$A \cap \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \} = \{ \langle x, \inf\left(\mu_A(x), \frac{1}{2}\right), \sup\left(\nu_A(x), \frac{1}{2}\right) \rangle / x \in E \}$$

$$A \cap \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \} = \{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \}$$

$$A \cap \{ \langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \rangle / x \in E \} = ?(A).$$

(d) $!(?(A)) = !(\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \})$

$$!(?(A)) = \{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right)\right) \rangle / x \in E \}$$

$$!(? (A)) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right\rangle / x \in E \right\} \tag{1}$$

$$?(!(A)) = ? \left(\left\{ \left\langle x, \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\} \right)$$

$$?(!(A)) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x) \right) \right), \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x) \right) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$?(!(A)) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right\rangle / x \in E \right\} \tag{2}$$

From (1) and (2), we have $!(? (A)) = ? (!(A)) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$.

Theorem 3.2: For every two *ILFS* A and B , we have

(a) $!(A \cap B) = !(A) \cap !(B)$,

(b) $!(A \cup B) = !(A) \cup !(B)$,

(c) $?(A \cup B) = ?(A) \cup ?(B)$,

(d) $?(A \cap B) = ?(A) \cap ?(B)$.

Proof:

(a) $!(A \cap B) = ! \left(\left\{ \left\langle x, \inf (\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)), \sup (\nu_A(x), \nu_B(x)) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\} \right)$

$$!(A \cap B) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \inf (\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \sup (\nu_A(x), \nu_B(x)) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$!(A \cap B) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \inf \left(\sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x) \right), \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_B(x) \right) \right), \sup \left(\inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_B(x) \right) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$!(A \cap B) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\} \cap \left\{ \left\langle x, \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_B(x) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_B(x) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$!(A \cap B) = !(A) \cap !(B).$$

(b) $!(A \cup B) = ! \left(\left\{ \left\langle x, \sup (\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)), \inf (\nu_A(x), \nu_B(x)) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\} \right)$

$$!(A \cup B) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \sup (\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \inf (\nu_A(x), \nu_B(x)) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$!(A \cup B) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \sup \left(\sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x) \right), \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_B(x) \right) \right), \inf \left(\inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_B(x) \right) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$!(A \cup B) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\} \cup \left\{ \left\langle x, \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_B(x) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_B(x) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$!(A \cup B) = !(A) \cup !(B).$$

(c) $?(A \cap B) = ? \left(\left\{ \left\langle x, \inf (\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)), \sup (\nu_A(x), \nu_B(x)) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\} \right)$

$$?(A \cap B) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \inf (\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)) \right), \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \sup (\nu_A(x), \nu_B(x)) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$?(A \cap B) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \inf \left(\inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x) \right), \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_B(x) \right) \right), \sup \left(\sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x) \right), \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_B(x) \right) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} ?(A \cap B) &= \left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \cap \\ &\quad \left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_B(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_B(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$?(A \cap B) = ?(A) \cap ?(B).$$

$$(d) ?(A \cup B) = ?(\{ \langle x, \sup(\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)), \inf(\nu_A(x), \nu_B(x)) \rangle / x \in E \})$$

$$?(A \cup B) = \left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \sup(\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x))\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \inf(\nu_A(x), \nu_B(x))\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} ?(A \cup B) &= \left\{ \langle x, \sup\left(\inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_B(x)\right)\right), \right. \\ &\quad \left. \inf\left(\sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_B(x)\right)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} ?(A \cup B) &= \left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \cup \\ &\quad \left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_B(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_B(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$?(A \cup B) = ?(A) \cup ?(B).$$

Theorem 3.3: For any *ILFS* A , we have

$$(a) \square! A = !\square A,$$

$$(b) \square? A = ?\square A,$$

$$(c) \diamond! A = !\diamond A,$$

$$(d) \diamond? A = ?\diamond A.$$

Proof:

$$(a) \square! A = \square \left(\left\{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \right)$$

$$\square! A = \left\{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), N\left(\sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\square! A = \left\{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, N(\mu_A(x))\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\square! A = !\square A.$$

$$(b) \square? A = \square \left(\left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \right)$$

$$\square? A = \left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), N\left(\inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\square? A = \left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, N(\mu_A(x))\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\square? A = ?\square A.$$

$$(c) \diamond! A = \diamond \left(\left\{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \right)$$

$$\diamond! A = \left\{ \langle x, N\left(\inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right)\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\diamond! A = \left\{ \langle x, \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, N(\nu_A(x))\right), \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\diamond! A = !\diamond A.$$

$$(d) \diamond? A = \diamond \left(\left\{ \langle x, \inf\left(\frac{1}{2}, \mu_A(x)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\} \right)$$

$$\diamond? A = \left\{ \langle x, N\left(\sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right)\right), \sup\left(\frac{1}{2}, \nu_A(x)\right) \rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\diamond A = \left\{ \left\langle x, \inf \left(\frac{1}{2}, N(v_A(x)) \right), \sup \left(\frac{1}{2}, v_A(x) \right) \right\rangle / x \in E \right\}$$

$$\diamond A = ? \diamond A.$$

4. Conclusion:

In this paper, we have introduced the Level operators on Intuitionistic L-Fuzzy sets [ILFS] and established some of their properties. In future we will study some more operators on ILFS and their applications.

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